

Supporting Information

Synthesis of Picolylamine-Functionalized Graphene via Fluorographene Chemistry for High- Performance Symmetric Supercapacitors

Iosif Tantis,^{1,2} Demetrios D. Chronopoulos,^{,3} Vítězslav Hrubý,^{2,4} Nikolaos Chalmes,¹ Ondřej Tomanec,²
Aristides Bakandritsos,^{2,5} Emmanuel P. Giannelis^{*,1}*

¹Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Cornell University, Ithaca, New York 14850, United States

²Regional Centre of Advanced Technologies and Materials, Czech Advanced Technology and Research Institute (CATRIN), Palacky University, Slechtitelu 27, Olomouc 77900, Czech Republic

³Laboratory of Organic Chemistry, Department of Chemistry, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, 15771 Athens, Greece

⁴Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Palacky University, 17. listopadu 1192/12, Olomouc 77900, Czech Republic

⁵Nanotechnology Centre, Centre for Energy and Environmental Technologies, VSB–Technical University of Ostrava, 17. listopadu 2172/15, Poruba 708 00 Ostrava, Czech Republic

*Correspondence to E.P.G. (epg2@cornell.edu), D.C.C. (dchrono@chem.uoa.gr)

1. Experimental section

1.1 Reagents and materials

Fluorinated graphite (GrF) (C:F 1:1.1, >61 wt. %F), 2-picolyamine, triethylamine and 1,2-dichlorobenzene (oDCB) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and were used as received without purification.

1.2 Synthesis of G-Npyr

In a typical procedure, 1.0 g (~32.2 mmol, calculation based on C-F units) of GrF was placed in a round-bottom glass flask containing 100 mL of oDCB. The suspension of GrF was dispersed by stirring for 72 h and sonication for an additional 4 h. Afterwards, 12 mL (116.0 mmol) of 2-picolyamine was added to the flask and the mixture was stirred for 30 min. To enhance the nucleophilicity and assure the deprotonation of 2-picolamine's amino group, 1.50 mL of triethylamine was added in the flask. Afterwards, the mixture was placed in an oil bath at 90 °C under stirring for 48 h. After the completion of the reaction, the solid product was centrifuged and purified by repeated centrifugal washings with ethanol, dichloromethane, acetone and ultrapure water.

2. Characterization techniques

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra were recorded using an iS5 FTIR spectrometer (Thermo Nicolet) equipped with a Smart Orbit ZnSe ATR accessory. A droplet of the ethanol-dispersed material was placed on a ZnSe crystal and allowed to dry. Spectra were acquired by summing 64 scans while maintaining a nitrogen gas flow through the ATR accessory, followed by baseline correction. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was conducted using a PHI VersaProbe II spectrometer (Physical Electronics) with an Al K α source (15 kV, 50 W). Data analysis and spectra deconvolution was performed with the MultiPak software package (Ulvac - PHI, Inc.). SEM images were obtained using a Zeiss Gemini 500 SEM. Raman spectroscopy was carried out on a DXR Raman microscope (Thermo Scientific) using a 633 nm diode laser as the excitation source. AFM experiments were conducted in peak force tapping

mode on a Multimode 8, Nanoscope 6 system using RTESPA-525 cantilevers with a tip radius of 8 nm. Before the AFM measurements, the sample was sonicated for 30 min in ethanol and drop-casted onto silicon wafers. The p-type, single side polished Si wafers (Pure Wafer), were cleaned for 15 min in an ultrasonic bath with water, acetone and ethanol. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out using a Netzsch STA 449C Jupiter thermal analyzer instrument. ~5 mg of each sample was loaded in an α -Al₂O₃ open crucible and heated under N₂ flow (100 mL min⁻¹). A temperature ramp from 45 to 990 °C with heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ was used. High Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy (HR-TEM) and scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) were carried out with a Titan G2 60-300 (FEI) microscope operating at 80 kV. HR-TEM images were taken with UltraScan 1000XP CCD camera (Gatan). STEM images were taken with high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) detector 3000 (Fishione). Energy Dispersive Spectrometry (EDS) mapping was performed in STEM mode using the Super-X system with four silicon drift detectors (Bruker).

3. Electrochemical measurements

Electrochemical testing was conducted on a Bio-Logic instrument (BCS-810) and exported using a BT-Lab software 1.67. Three-electrode cell configurations were used to initially evaluate the electrochemical properties and the capacitive response of G-Npyr. In this system, a glassy carbon electrode (GCE) was used as the working electrode, a platinum wire served as the counter electrode, and a Ag/AgCl electrode was employed as the reference electrode. The material was casted on the GCE by drop-coating: a 10 μ L drop of a powder suspension (2 g L⁻¹) was coated onto the GCE surface and allowed to dry at ambient temperature to form a thin film adding a small portion of poly-vinylidene fluoride (PVDF, Sigma-Aldrich) to achieve better adhesion. 1 M H₂SO₄ was used as the electrolyte solution in all experiments. Cyclic voltammograms were taken at a fixed potential of 0-1 V vs Ag/AgCl at various sweep rates and galvanostatic charge-discharge (GDC) at the same potential and various current densities. To prepare the electrodes for the 2-electrode configuration, the active material was initially dispersed in N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP, p.a. \geq 99%, Sigma-Aldrich) adding PVDF as a binder and a conductive carbon (Ketjen Black) in a ratio of 85:10:5.

The mixture was placed in a bath sonicator for 1 hour and then homogenized using a planetary mixer (Thinky Mixer ARV-310, Thinky Corporation). This process was repeated three times to ensure uniformity. Afterwards, the slurry became homogeneous and was pasted on aluminum foil coated with carbon using a 180 μm dr. blade. The casted thin film was dried at 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a vacuum oven overnight, before two electrodes with diameter 18 mm were cut and pressed in between two stainless steel metal plates with a force ~ 80 kN for 1 minute. The final electrodes were dried again at 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under vacuum for 3 hours to remove any trapped humidity before being transferred in an Ar filled glovebox. The two electrodes were placed in an El-Cell between a Whatman glass microfiber paper separator. The separator was soaked with 90-100 μl of 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate (EMIM- BF_4), which was used as electrolyte. Before actual testing of the material, conditioning was performed by holding a potential of 1.2 V for 5 minutes, then running 10 cycles at 0.5 A g^{-1} up to 3 V and running another 100 cycles at current density 1 A g^{-1} up to 3.5 V.

The specific capacitance of the active material (C_s , F g^{-1}) and volumetric capacitance (C_v , F cm^{-3}) was calculated from GCD discharge curve using the equations below:

$$C_s = 2 \times ((I \cdot t)/(m \cdot V))$$

$$C_v = (C_s(m / \text{Vel}))$$

where I is the discharge current, t is discharging time (IR-drop was excluded), m is the mass of the active material on one electrode, V is potential window, and Vel is the volume of the material on the electrode.

Gravimetric and volumetric energy density and power density were calculated as follows:

$$E_g = (C_s \times V^2)/ 28.8 [\text{Wh kg}^{-1}]$$

$$P_g = (E_g/t)3600 [\text{W kg}^{-1}]$$

$$E_v = (C_v \times V^2)/ 28.8 [\text{Wh L}^{-1}]$$

$$P_v = (E_v/t)3600 [W L^{-1}]$$

4. Calculation of the functionalization degree (FD) of G-Npyr combining TGA and XPS data

The total mass loss of G-Npyr at ~ 1000 °C was 35.3 wt. %, and the residual mass was 64.7 wt. % (Figure 2f). The loss of oxygen impurities (5.1 wt. %) was subtracted from the total mass loss resulting in 30.2 wt. %) assigned to the Npyr units and the residual fluorine. In order to calculate the fluorine in our sample, the XPS data were used. According to the elemental composition of G-Npyr derived from XPS analysis (Figure 2c) corresponded to the formula $C_{82}N_{9.6}O_{3.5}F_{4.4}$ with a molecular weight of 1264 g/mol. From the formula and the molecular weight of G-Npyr, the fluorine content in G-Npyr was estimated at 6.6 wt. %. The amount of fluorine (6.6 wt. %) was subtracted from the total percentage resulting in 23.6 wt. % of Npyr units. From the molecular weight of Npyr (107.14 g/mol) we calculate $(23.6 \text{ g Npyr})/(107.14 \text{ g Npyr/mol})$ 24 carbon atoms/molecule of Npyr or 4.1 molecules of Npyr/100 graphene carbon atoms resulting in an FD of G-Npyr of ~ 4.1 .

5. Additional characterization data

Figure S1. XPS survey spectrum of GrF with its composition indicated in the inset.

Table S1. Results on the deconvolution of the N 1s HR-XPS spectrum of G-Npyr material.

configuration	Binding energy (eV)	FWHM (eV)	Area (%)
Pyridinic N	398.71	1.36	39.41
C-NH-C	399.70	1.43	42.29
Tertiary/quaternary N	401.11	1.59	18.3

Figure S2. (a) N₂ porosimetry measurements for GrF (black) and GNpyr (red); (b) DFT pore volume distributions based on the N₂-carbon slit-cylinder kernel for GrF and GNpyr.

Figure S3. Additional SEM images with the corresponding chemical mapping in (a) low and (b) high magnification for the G-Npyr

Figure S4. Elemental EDS analysis for the G-Npyr

Figure S5. AFM thickness distribution of G-Npyr sheets.

Figure S6. A representative HR-TEM image of G-Npyr.

Figure S7. A representative EDS fluorine map of G-Npyr.

Figure S8. Gravimetric Ragone plots comparing G-Npyr with other recent studies on carbon-based materials as electrodes in supercapacitors working with IL electrolytes.¹⁻

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